

EFFECT OF PANCHAKARMA IN THE MANAGEMENT OF JALODARA (ASCITES): A
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ABSTRACT

Background: Classical *Ayurvedic* texts including those of *Charaka*, *Sushruta*, and *Vagbhata* classify *Udara* among the *Mahagada*, highlighting its chronic-complex nature. *Yakritodara* is one among eight types of *Udara* where main cause being *Mandagni*, which leads to *Jalodara* in later stages. *Jalodara* closely resembles Ascites, which is defined as the pathological accumulation of fluid in the peritoneal cavity. **Aim:** To evaluate the role of *Ayurvedic* treatment in *Jalodara*. **Material and Methods:** A 60-year-old male presented to the OPD with complaints of abdominal distention, anorexia, sour belching, and occasional respiratory distress. The patient was managed according to the *Samanya Chikitsa Sutra* of *Udara roga*. Initial treatment focused on *Agni Deepana* using *Ajamodadi Churna*, followed by *Nitya Virechana* with *Gomutra Haritaki* for 7 days & *Udara Lepa* with *Gomutra Haritaki* for 10 days was also done. The patient was also advised to follow a diet regimen including *Ksheera Paana* as part of *Pathya Ahara*. **Result:** All presenting symptoms showed marked improvement following treatment. The abdominal girth at the umbilical level, which measured 89 cm prior to intervention, reduced to 73 cm after treatment and during follow-up. Additionally, abdominal ultrasonography findings that initially indicated mild ascites and splenomegaly showed complete resolution in the post-treatment USG assessment. **Discussion & Conclusion:** As *Agnimandhya* is considered as primary etiological factor in this condition, initial management was focused on *Agnideepana*. This was followed by *Nitya Virechana*, which facilitated the elimination of *Pitta Dosha*, *Raktaprasadana*, *Vataanulomana*. *Udara Lepa* contributed to the reduction of accumulated fluid. Additionally, *Nitya Ksheera Sevnam* which possesses *Rechaka* properties, supported the therapeutic process.

KEYWORDS: *Jalodara*, Ascites, *Nitya virechana*, *Udara lepa*, *Yakrit vikara*, *Udara roga*.**INTRODUCTION**

In *Ayurveda*, *Yakrit* (liver) is described as one of the *Koshtangas* and is defined in *Shabdastomahanidhi* as “*Yam Samyaman Karoti Iti Yakrit*,” signifying its role in regulating physiological functions. Classical *Ayurvedic* texts do not describe *Yakrit Vikaras* as a separate disease entity. *Acharya Charaka* states that the descriptions of *Pliha* are equally applicable to *Yakrit*,^[1] a view also endorsed by *Sushruta Samhita*.

Ayurvedic literature describes various liver-related conditions based on structural and morphological

changes, such as *Yakrit Vriddhi*, *Yakritodara*,^[2] *Yakritgata Dosha*, *Yakrit Kshaya*, *Yakrit Vidradhi*, and *Yakrit Granthi*. Functional hepatic disorders are described in terms of clinical manifestations, including *Kamala*,^[3] *Kumbha kamala*,^[4] *Panaki*, and *Halimaka*.^[5]

Udara Roga, classified under *Ashta Mahagada*,^[6] is a *Tridoshaja Vyadhi* characterized by the accumulation of *Doshas* and *Malas* in the abdominal region. The classical principle “रोगाः सर्वे अपि मन्दे अग्नौ सुतराम् उदराणि च।”^[7] highlights *Mandagni* as the primary etiological factor. Impaired *Agni* and increased *Mala* lead to vitiation of

Prana, *Apana Vayu*, and *Agni*, resulting in *Srotorodha* of *Ambuvaha* and *Swedavaha Srotas*. Aggravated *Vata* accumulates between *Twaka* and *Mamsa*, causing abdominal distension.

Three stages of *Udara Roga* are described: *Ajatodaka Avastha*, *Picchavastha*, and *Jatodaka Avastha*, the last representing advanced disease. Common features include abdominal distension, emaciation, poor digestion, reduced strength, fatigue, and anxiety. Management primarily includes *Nitya Virechana*, *Agnideepana*, and appropriate dietary measures such as *Ksheera Pana* and *Takra Sevana* to reverse the pathogenesis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design: Single-case clinical study.

Patient Information: A 60-year-old married male patient former by occupation with middle income group, presented to the Panchakarma outpatient department with complaints of progressive abdominal distention for the past three months.

History of Present Illness: A 60-year-old male, with no known history of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) or hypertension (HTN), but with a long-standing history of chronic alcoholism, was apparently in normal health until three months prior to presentation. He visited our outpatient department (OPD) with complaints of progressive abdominal distention for the past three months, accompanied by anorexia, sour belching, occasional respiratory discomfort, low backache, constipation, and disturbed sleep for the last one and a half to two months. He had previously taken treatment at an allopathic hospital, where he was prescribed diuretics,

INVESTIGATION: Before Treatment (30/5/24)

Table 1: Blood investigation Before Treatment 30/5/24.

PARAMETRS	VALUES
SERUM CREATININE	0.9Mg/dl
SER BIL. TOTAL AND DIRECT	1.9 Mg/dl
SGOT	34.1 IU/L
SGPT	26.5 IU/L
ALKALINE PHOSPHATE	78.0 IU/L
TOTLA PROTEIN	7.1 mg/dl
ALBUMIN	2.9 mg/dl
GLOBULIN	4.2 mg/dl
A/G RATIO	0.6

USG Abd Impression: (9/5/24)

Ultrasonography of the abdomen reveals features suggestive of chronic parenchymal liver disease with early cirrhotic changes. The portal vein appears prominent with the presence of a few mesenteric

but did not experience significant relief. Consequently, he approached our hospital for further evaluation and Ayurvedic management.

Family History: No significant family history was noted

Personal History: History of chronic alcoholic since 10 to 12 years. The patient followed a mixed diet. Appetite was reduced, sleep was disturbed, and bowel habits were irregular, characterized by constipation.

General Examination: On general examination, the patient had a moderate build and was moderately nourished. The patient's height was 5 feet 2 inches and body weight was 57 kg. Pallor, icterus, and clubbing were absent. Bilateral pedal oedema was present (++).

Systemic Examination

- **Central Nervous System:** Higher mental functions intact; cranial nerves, motor and sensory systems within normal limits.
- **Cardiovascular System:** Normal S1 and S2; no murmurs.
- **Respiratory System:** Bilateral normal vesicular breath sounds with no added sounds
- **Per Abdomen**
 - ✓ **Inspection-**Distended abdomen, stretched umbilicus.
 - ✓ **Palpation-**Tenderness ++, abdominal girth-90cm at umbilical level.
 - ✓ **Percussion-** Fluid thrill test – positive, Shifting dullness present

collaterals, raising suspicion of portal hypertension. Mild splenomegaly is noted along with mild ascites. Additionally, a simple cyst is observed in the right kidney.

Figure 2: Showing USG Abdomen Report before treatment.

Figure 3: Showing blood investigation report before treatment.

Diagnosis: Based on clinical features, Ayurvedic assessment, and investigative findings, the case was diagnosed as *Jalodara*.

INTERVENTION

Table 2: Intervention.

TREATMENT	MEDICINES	KALA	ANUPANA	DURATION
DEEPANA-PACHANA	Ajamodadi churna	½ tsp tid-b/f	Ushna Jala	3 days
NITYA VIRECHANA	Gomutra Haritaki	1tab morning	Ksheera	7 days
UDARA LEPA	Gomutra Haritaki	Q S		10 days

SHAMANA AUSHADI -For 15 days

Table 3: Shamanaushadhi.

NAME	DOSE
SHANKHA VATI	1-0-1 (before food)
ABHAYARISHTA	10ML-0-10ML (after food)

RESULTS

SUBJECTIVE PARAMETERS

Table 4: Comparison of Subjective parameter Before -after treatment & After follow up.

Parameters	BT	AT	AF
Anorexia	+++	Nil	Nil
Sour belching	++	Nil	Nil
Respiratory distress	++	Nil	Nil
Pain in Lowback & Flank region	+++	+	Nil
Sleep quality	+++	Nil	Nil
Constipation	+++	Nil	Nil

Anorexia and sour belching showed marked reduction from the second day of treatment. Constipation was

relieved by the fourth day of therapy. There were no complaints of respiratory distress, and pain in the lower

back and flank region was also reduced. The patient peacefully reported improved sleep quality and was able to sleep

OBJECTIVE PARAMETERS

1. Umbilical girth

Table 5: Umbilical girth.

DATE	4CM BELOW UMBILICUS (CM)	AT UMBILICUS (CM)	4CM ABOVE UMBILICUS (CM)
10/5/24	92	90	88
11/5/24	91	89	87.8
12/5/24	89.5	86	85
14/5/24	88	84	83.6
16/5/24	85	80	79
18/5/24	80.5	75	74
22/5/24	80	73	73

2. USG Abd IMPRESSION: (13/6/24 AFTER FOLLOW UP)

- No evidence of Ascites & No splenomegaly

3. LIVER FUNCTION TEST-14/06/24

Table 6: Blood investigation after treatment 14/6/24.

SER BIL. TOTAL AND DIRECT	1.6 Mg/dl
SGOT	28.5IU/L
SGPT	19.2IU/L
ALKALINE PHOSPHATE	58.9IU/L
TOTLA PROTEIN	5.9mg/dl
ALBUMIN	2.7mg/dl
GLOBULIN	3.2mg/dl

SHREE DURGA DIAGNOSTIC LAB		
First Floor, Jnani Complex, Ananthapura Road, Opp. Taranath Govt. Ayurvedic Medical College & Hospital, BALLARI, Call: 78925-35689		
Patient Name: ESHWARAPP, 60 YRS / M	Lab No.: 113	Reported: 14/06/24
Ref. By Dr.: SHIVAGOWD HEGARU		
TEST NAME	RESULT	NORMAL VALUE
LIVER FUNCTION TEST		
SERUM BILIRUBIN TOTAL	1.6 mg/dl	0.0 - 1.2 mg/dl
SERUM BILIRUBIN DIRECT	0.4 mg/dl	0.0 - 0.4 mg/dl
SGOT	28.5 IU/L	10 - 40 IU/L
SGPT	19.2 IU/L	10 - 30 IU/L
ALKALINE PHOSPHATASE	58.9 IU/L	10 - 120 IU/L
TOTAL PROTEIN	5.9 mg/dl	6.0 - 8.0 mg/dl
ALBUMIN	2.7 mg/dl	3.5 - 5.2 mg/dl
GLOBULIN	3.2 mg/dl	
ASPARTATE	0.0	

Figure 3: Showing Improvement in blood report after treatment.

Figure 4: Showing USG Abdominal report After the treatment.

Figure 5: Showing Distended Abdomen before treatment.

Figure 6: Showing Distended Abdomen After treatment.

FOLLOW UP

After 15 days, no above said complaints were present and abdominal girth remained the same i.e 73 cm (at the Umbilical level)

DISCUSSION

According to *Ayurveda*, *Jalodara* is a *Tridoshaja* disorder with predominance of *Kapha* and *Pitta*, originating from *Mandagni*. Indulgence in *Nidana* such as excessive alcohol consumption, *Ati-lavana*, *Ati-amla*, *Ati-ushna ahara*, and irregular dietary habits leads to impairment of *Jatharagni* and formation of *Ama*. This *Ama* vitiates the *Doshas* and causes *Srotorodha*, particularly in *Rasavaha*, *Annavaha*, and *Udakavaha Srotas*. *Pitta Dushti* involving *Yakrit* (the *Mula Sthana* of *Rakta*) further disrupts metabolic and fluid regulation. Obstruction of channels hampers proper absorption and circulation of fluids, resulting in accumulation of *Apya Dosh* within the abdominal cavity.

Progressively, deranged *Agni*, *Dosha Sanchaya*, and *Srotas Dushti* manifest clinically as abdominal distension, heaviness, edema, and other classical features

of *Jalodara*. In modern terms, *Mandagni* correlates with impaired hepatic metabolic function, *Yakrit Dushti* corresponds to chronic liver disease, and *Srotorodha* can be equated with portal hypertension and altered hepatic circulation. Accumulation of *Apya Dosh* reflects sodium and water retention due to neurohormonal activation and hypoalbuminemia. Thus, the *Ayurvedic Samprapti* of *Jalodara* closely parallels the modern pathophysiology of ascites.

1. NIDANA PARIMARJANA

Nidana Parimarjana is considered the first and most essential step in the management of *Udararoga*. In the present case, long-standing alcohol consumption, improper dietary habits, and weakened digestive fire were identified as major etiological factors contributing to *Yakrit Dushti* and *Apya Dosh Sanchaya*.

1. IMPORTANCE OF DEEPANA- PACHANA

Mandagni is the prime pathological factor in *Jalodara*. Impaired digestion leads to *Ama* formation, which causes *Srotorodha* and further accumulation of fluid. Hence, correction of *Agni* is indispensable for successful

management. Therefore, *Agnideepana* was initiated as the primary line of treatment, addressing the root cause of the condition. The chosen formulation included multiple herbs possessing *Ushna Veerya*, such as *Ajamoda*, *Vidanga*, *Pippali*, *Pippalimoola*, *Devadaru*, *Chitraka*, *Shatpushpa*, *Maricha*, *Haritaki*, *Vridhdharu*, and *Shunthi*. These ingredients predominantly exhibit *Katu* (pungent) and *Tikta* (bitter) tastes, which are known to stimulate digestion and enhance *Agni*. By enhancing *Jatharagni*, *Ajamodadi Churna* prevents further production of pathological fluid and initiates *Samprapti Vighatana*. These combined actions contributed to the alleviation of symptoms such as anorexia, sour belching, and constipation.

2. IMPORTANCE OF NITYA VIRECHANA

Nitya Virechana is a type of *Virechana Karma* (therapeutic purgation) administered daily in *Alpa Bala Rogi*, using purgative formulations (*Virechaka Aushadha*). It is specifically designed for the gradual elimination of excessively aggravated *Doshas* (*Bahu Dosh*) in small quantities (*Stoka Stoka Dosh Nirharana*), and serves as an *Atyayika Chikitsa* (emergency or immediate line of treatment).

In *Jalodara*, the pathology involves excessive accumulation of *Doshas* (*Dosha Atimatra Upachaya*) and obstruction of bodily channels (*Srotomarga Nirodha*). Hence, classical texts emphasize the need for regular purgation therapy with the instruction: “*Nityam eva virechayet*” daily administration of *Virechana* is essential for effective management. *Nitya Virechana* also aids in reducing abdominal girth and associated edema by promoting the elimination of excess fluid from the peritoneal cavity. In modern medicine, diuretics are commonly used to address fluid accumulation; however, while they may reduce existing fluid, they do not prevent further accumulation. In contrast, *Ayurvedic Nitya Virechana* therapy not only evacuates retained fluid but also helps to arrest its further accumulation by correcting the underlying *Dosha* imbalance.

The liver (*Yakrit*), considered the *Mula Sthana* of *Rakta Dhatu*, is closely associated with *Pitta Dosha*. Due to the *Ashraya-Ashrayi Sambandha* between *Rakta* and *Pitta*, *Nitya Virechana* serves as the ideal therapy to eliminate vitiated *Pitta*, which plays a key role in the pathogenesis of *Jalodara*. In the present case, *Gomutra Haritaki* was used for *Nitya Virechana*. *Gomutra* possesses *Ushna*, *Tikshna*, and *Ruksha* properties, which help in breaking *Srotosanga* and enhancing *Agni*. *Haritaki* is *Anulomana* and *Tridoshahara*, facilitating gentle and controlled purgation.

The combined action of *Gomutra Haritaki* resulted in effective elimination of accumulated fluid, reduction in abdominal girth, and improvement in associated symptoms without causing dehydration or electrolyte imbalance. The gradual and sustained reduction in abdominal distension observed in this case highlights the

significance of *Nitya Virechana* in *Jalodara* management.

3. IMPORTANCE OF UDARA LEPA

Udara Lepa is an important external therapeutic measure advocated in *Udararoga*, especially in *Jalodara*, to facilitate localized action. This *Lepa* gives added effect by decreasing the fluid accumulation due to the *Karshana guna* of *Gomutra haritaki*.

5. IMPORTANCE OF SHAMANA AUSHADHI

After *Shodhana Chikitsa*, *Shamana Aushadhi* are essential to stabilize the achieved results and prevent recurrence. *Shankha Vati* and *Abhayarishtha* were administered to maintain digestive strength and bowel regularity.

Shankha Vati possesses *Deepana*, *Pachana*, and *Anulomana* properties, preventing re-accumulation of *Ama*. *Abhayarishtha* supports gut motility and sustains *Agni Bala*.

6. IMPORTANCE OF KSHEERA PATHYA

Accordingly, strict dietary regulation was advised, and the patient was maintained on *Ksheera Pathya*. *Ksheera* is *Laghu*, *Deepana*, *Balya*, and *Rasayana* in nature, and is described as *Srishtavinmutra*, facilitating mild purgation and elimination of excess extracellular fluid. This diet helped maintain adequate nutrition while reducing metabolic burden on the liver and preventing further *Dosha* aggravation and fluid accumulation, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of subsequent therapeutic interventions.

CONCLUSION

Jalodara, a grave condition described under *Udararoga*, is a *Tridoshaja* disorder in which *Mandagni*, *Dosha Prakopa*, and *Srotorodha* play a key role in the accumulation of fluid in the abdominal cavity. Effective management therefore requires *Samprapti Vighatana*. In the present case, treatment based on classical *Ayurvedic* principles *Nidana Parimarjana*, *Agnideepana*, *Nitya Virechana*, *Udara Lepa*, and *Shamana Aushadhi* resulted in significant clinical and investigational improvement, suggesting that a systematic *Ayurvedic* approach can be effective in the management of *Jalodara*.

REFERENCES

1. Agnivesha charaka samhita, ayurveda deepika commentary of chakrapani edited by vaidya Yadav ji Tsrikamji acharya, chikitsa sthana 13, chaukamba Krishna das academy, Varanasi, 2015; 134.
2. Agnivesha charaka samhita, ayurveda deepika commentary of chakrapani edited by vaidya Yadav ji Trikamji acharya, chikitsa sthana 13/21, chaukamba Krishna das academy, Varanasi, 2015; 142.
3. Agnivesha charaka samhita, ayurveda deepika commentary of chakrapani edited by vaidya Yadav ji Trikamji acharya, chikitsa sthana 16/34-36,

- chaukamba Krishna das academy, Varanasi, 2015; 234.
4. Agnivesha charaka samhita, ayurveda deepika commentary of chakrapani edited by vaidya Yadav ji Trikamji acharya, chiktsa sthana 16/37-39, chaukamba Krishna das academy, Varanasi, 2015; 234.
 5. Agnivesha charaka samhita, ayurveda deepika commentary of chakrapani edited by vaidya Yadav ji Trikamji acharya, chiktsa sthana 16/132-134, chaukamba Krishna das academy, Varanasi, 2015; 246.
 6. Kaviraj Dr.Ambikadutta Shastri, Sushrutha Samhita, Vol 1, Chaukambha Sanskrit Sansthana, Varanasi, 2018; 163.
 7. Acharya Vagbhata Ashtanga Hridaya with the commentaries Sarvanga Sundara of Arunadatta & Ayurveda Rasayana of Hemadri, Annotated by Dr.Anna Moreswar Kunte and Krisna Ramacahandra Shastri Navri, Edited Pt Hari Sadashiva Shastri edition-2018, Choukambha Surabhi Prakashana Varanasi, Nidana Sthana 12/1.